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Air starvation experiments and simulation in PEMFC stacks

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Abstract

One of the remaining challenges of commercialization of fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV) is the freeze start. The main target of this highly dynamic scenario is to heat up the stack before the start fails due to icing of the cells. Unassisted freeze start operating strategies are currently state of the art to solve this problem. Starting with air starvation is one successful operating strategy. In this case, the fuel cell stack is deliberately undersupplied with air (air understoic operation point) in order to reduce the efficiency and therefore produce more heat. During freeze starts both the freezing of cell parts as well as the kinetics play an important role in addition to the operating strategy itself. These different effects lead to non-uniform internal states in the individual cells as well as to inhomogeneities between the cells. To be able to observe these different processes separately and thus to better understand them, air starvation experiments were carried out under normal operation conditions. In this way, the effects due to air starvation can be analyzed individually without having to consider effects due to kinetic limitation or icing. In addition, a 2D+1D PEMFC stack model has been developed to explain this phenomenon qualitatively.

Fig. 1 U-I characteristic curve for air overstoic operation (blue) and air understoic operation (orange). With air understoic operation, the efficiency of cell deteriorates due to increased diffusion losses.

Introduction

In times of increasingly extreme climate change, it is necessary to find and use alternative, (nearly) emission-free driving systems for automotive applications. One promising solution is the proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) as a power generation device. The PEMFC converts the chemical energy of hydrogen and air into electrical energy, producing only water as a byproduct. Its advantages include low operating temperatures, zero emissions, flexible sizing, and high efficiency [1-3]. Although extensive research has been conducted in the field of PEMFCs in recent years, several problems still need to be overcome before PEMFCs can be commercialized in the automotive sector. One of these problems, as with other applications, is the freeze start. As soon as the internal temperature of the PEMFC drops below the freezing point, the produced water freezes immediately and can block reactant gas paths or the catalytic layer. This can lead to degradation, structural damage, and even abort the start.

There are various options for reducing the potential damage described above and successfully starting from cold: First, drying before the actual start plays a major role. Gas purging removes as much water as possible before cell shutdown, preventing it from freezing during cooling [4,5]. However, another option is the selection of materials and design. The effect of various endplates [6], the flow-field design [7], and the material composition of the membrane electrode assembly (MEA) [8] were investigated.

Several methods for starting in cold conditions are already known in the literature. The most prominent are the keep-warm method, the unassisted freeze start, and the assisted freeze start [9]. With the keep-warm method, the stack is constantly kept at temperatures above 0°C to prevent ice formation and the associated problems. In contrast to the keep-warm method, with the assisted freeze-start, the stack cools down below zero degrees before starting. During start-up, the stack and/or the BOP components are heated using an external power source such as an electric heater and a battery [10-13]. These two approaches require additional components and thus result in additional costs. Therefore, in recent years, the focus has been on the so-called unassisted freeze start. As the name suggests, the stack and BOP components are brought to a normal operating temperature entirely without external heat input. The most prominent example of this method is Toyota's so-called rapid start-up operation method. In this case, the start-up occurs under reactant limitation at cathode side, which reduces the efficiency of the fuel cell and thus increases waste heat production [9].

Gas limitation is known as the reactant deficiency phenomenon during PEMFC operating processes and can occur on both the anode and cathode side of the fuel cell. In addition to the operating strategy mentioned above, the most common reasons for reactant deficiency include inappropriate flow field or manifold designs, manufacturing issues, or faulty operation of the entire fuel cell system [14-23]. A lack of reactants can lead to a variety of complications, such as carbon corrosion [22, 24-26], cell polarity reversal [27, 28], structural damage [29, 30], or even non-uniform thermal stress due to a heterogeneous distribution of physical parameters [31-33].

Hydrogen starvation is primarily responsible for the often-irreversible damages mentioned above. This is not considered in this paper because the oxygen supply is limited during the rapid start-up operation method. This leads to either local or even global oxygen starvation on the cathode. If this occurs, the normal electrochemical reaction, namely $H_2 \rightarrow 2H^+ + 2e^-$ and $2H^+ + 2e^- + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow H_2O$, can no longer take place. The hydrogen ions from the anode recombine to form elemental hydrogen on the cathode and thus "pump" hydrogen from anode to cathode [34]. This hydrogen pump phenomenon is far less harmful than hydrogen starvation, but it can also lead to a heterogeneous distribution of physical parameters and thus to uneven thermal and humidification stress, cell reversals, performance losses during operation, and irreversible component damage.

In order to separately address mechanisms of air starvation, this paper focuses on temperatures above 0°. In this way, these effects can be analyzed individually without having to consider effects due to kinetics or icing. For this purpose, air starvation tests are carried out on a fuel cell system. The tests show that both the fuel cell reaction and the hydrogen pump phenomenon occur simultaneously in the stack.

Since up to now only separate models have been used for the fuel cell reaction and the proton pump, a 2D+1D PEMFC stack model was developed that considers both reaction types simultaneously in a cell at stack level.

1. Mathematical model

1.1. Model assumptions

To investigate air starvation in a fuel cell system, a 2D+1D PEMFC stack model was developed. To simplify the calculation, the following assumptions were made:

- All gas species are considered as ideal gases.
- The reactant and vapor are mixed uniformly.
- The flow in this model is incompressible.
- The effect of gravity is neglected.
- The phase change of water between gaseous and liquid states occurs instantaneously. Both phases are therefore in equilibrium.
- The electric potential is identical all over the surface of the bipolar plate due to the high electrical conductivity of the metal material.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the 2D+1D multiphase PEM fuel cell model with counter flow configuration of anode and cathode gases.

The 2D+1D multiphase PEM fuel cell model represents a counterflow configuration of the two reactant gases. The coolant flows in the same direction as the cathode gas. The individual cells are divided into the following layers according to the structural features: Channel, BP, GDL, CL and membrane, respectively on both anode and cathode side.

As the gases are consumed, the concentration of the individual gas components changes in the direction of flow. Since, as will be described in detail later, the cell voltage and, with it, the local current density in the fuel cell depend heavily on the local reactant concentration, it is essential to consider the individual layers of the fuel cell in segments to take the progression of the physical quantities into account. In the 2D+1D model, the variation of the physical quantities in depth (y-direction) is neglected. As just described, the cell is segmented into N elements along the gas flow (x-direction), and the physical quantities are summarized through plane (z-direction) into one parameter per layer.

The following are inputs to the model: the required current I_{set} , the temperatures and pressures of the reactants ($T_{an,ca}$ and $p_{an,ca}$) and the coolant (T_{cool} and p_{cool}), the humidity of the reactants ($a_{an,ca}$) and their stoichiometry ($\lambda_{an,ca}$).

1.2. Electrical model

1.2.1. Normal fuel cell operation

In normal fuel cell operation mode, multiple loss mechanisms occur and reduce the cell voltage U_{cell} . The voltage losses can be divided into three different groups: activation losses, ohmic losses and concentration losses [35].

$$U_{cell} = U_{rev} - \Delta U_{act} - \Delta U_{ohm} - \Delta U_{conc}$$

The reversible thermodynamic cell voltage U_{rev} of fuel cells can be calculated from the Gibbs free energy Δg , the Faraday's constant F , the ideal gas constant R , the partial pressures of H_2 and O_2 and the local operating temperature T and the reference temperature T_0 . This equation is also called the Nernst equation [36]:

$$U_{rev} = -\frac{\Delta g}{2F} + \frac{\Delta S_0}{2F}(T - T_0) + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(p_{H_2} p_{O_2}^{0.5})$$

The kinetic limitation of the reactions taking place on the surface of the electrodes causes activation losses U_{act} [35].

$$\Delta U_{act} = \frac{RT}{2\alpha F} \ln\left(\frac{i}{i_0}\right)$$

The activation losses are highly dependent on the drawn current density as well as temperature and the exchange current density. Since the cathode reaction is the main loss contributor, the exchange current density depends on the oxygen partial pressure p_{O_2} , the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) kinetic reaction order γ and the activation energy for the ORR [37]:

$$i_0 = i_{0,ref} \left(\frac{p_{O_2}}{p_{O_2,ref}}\right)^\gamma \exp\left(-\frac{E_{ca}^{rev}}{RT} \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_{ref}}\right)\right)$$

The ohmic losses U_{ohm} consist of the ohmic losses within the membrane that occur due to electron conduction. A distinction is made here between moisture-dependent (U_{mem}) and independent (U_{cont}) losses. Therefore, the proton conductivity of the membrane is strongly dependent on its water content [38].

$$\Delta U_{ohm} = \Delta U_{cont} + \Delta U_{mem} = i \left(r_{cont} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{ohm}}\right)$$

Concentration losses play a particularly important role during operation in (air) starvation. The fuel cell reaction leads to a reduction of reactants at the electrodes. In order to draw a certain current, a continuous, sufficient supply of gases to the electrodes must be ensured. Once the entire reactant flow at the electrodes has been consumed, the limiting current density is reached. This depends on the reactant partial pressure p_i in the channels, the gas diffusion coefficient D_i , and the GDL thickness δ_{GDL} , as well as the temperature T [39]:

$$i_{lim,i} = \frac{4FD_i p_i}{\delta_{GDL} RT}$$

This results in the concentration overpotential [35]:

$$\Delta U_{conc} = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln\left(\frac{i_{lim,H_2}}{i_{lim,H_2} - i}\right) + \frac{RT}{4F} \ln\left(\frac{i_{lim,O_2}}{i_{lim,O_2} - i}\right)$$

1.2.2. Hydrogen pump operation

If there is insufficient oxygen at the cathode to generate the desired current, the insufficient current must be compensated. For this, an alternative reaction to the fuel cell reaction must be used, which utilizes the hydrogen pump effect. Here, the hydrogen ions produced at the anode recombine again at the cathode after passing through the membrane: $2H^+(anode) + 2e^- = H_2(cathode)$ [40-42].

Like the conventional fuel cell reaction, the proton pump is an electrochemical reaction in which a potential difference occurs between the anode and cathode. The open-circuit voltage of the proton pump can be described using the Nernst equation [40]:

$$U_{rev,PP} = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{p_{H_2,an}}{p_{H_2,ca}} \right)$$

where F is the Faraday constant, $p_{H_2,ch,an}$ is the pressure on the anode side of the PEM fuel cell, and $p_{H_2,ch,ca}$ the pressure on the cathode side of the PEM fuel cell.

The total cell voltage is calculated equally to the cell voltage of the fuel cell reaction. The only difference is the calculation of the activation overpotential. Since the oxygen part of the reaction is missing, the activation potential depends only on the anode reaction.

The concentration overpotential is neglected here, since sufficient H_2 is always considered.

1.3. Thermal model

Based on Huo et al. [43] and Ramousse et al. [44], the source term for heat includes the reversible heat $S_{T,rev}$, the activation heat $S_{T,act}$, the ohmic heat $S_{T,ohm}$ and the latent heat $S_{T,lat}$.

$$S_T = \begin{cases} S_{T,ohm} + S_{T,lat} & \text{anode CL} \\ S_{T,ohm} + S_{T,lat} & \text{membrane} \\ S_{T,rev} + S_{T,act} + S_{T,ohm} + S_{T,lat} & \text{cathode CL} \\ S_{T,lat} & \text{GDL} \end{cases}$$

Therefore, it can be described with the following equations:

$$S_{T,rev} = -\frac{\Delta S T}{nF} i_{seg}$$

$$S_{T,act} = \eta_{act} i_{seg}$$

$$S_{T,ohm} = r_{mem} i_{seg}$$

$$S_{T,lat} = S_{i-j} h_{i-j}$$

Here, ΔS is the change in entropy ($\Delta S = -163 \text{ Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), r_{mem} proton transfer resistance (Ωm^{-2}), S_{i-j} ($\text{kmol m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$) and h_{i-j} (Jkg^{-1}) are the source term and latent heat for phase transitions between membrane water ($h_{mw-vap} = 2.308 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Jkg}^{-1}$) and vapor or liquid water and vapor ($h_{lq-vap} = 2.308 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Jkg}^{-1}$).

With these source terms, the energy conservation equation of fuel cells can be solved by [43]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left((\rho C_p)_{fl,sl}^{eff} T \right) = \frac{k_{fl,sl}^{eff} \partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + S_T$$

The left-hand side of the equation represents the effective volumetric heat capacity $(\rho C_p)_{fl,sl}^{eff}$ ($\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), the right-hand side the effective thermal conductivity $k_{fl,sl}^{eff}$ ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) as well as the source term of heat S_T .

1.4. Fluid model

1.4.1. Pressure loss calculation

In a typical fuel cell stack, the gases and coolant flow from the manifolds into the individual cells. This distribution depends on the pressure drop in the manifolds and the individual cells. Pressure drops in cells and in manifolds determine the respective partial pressure or mass flow through the individual cells, thus causing inhomogeneities within the stack and cells regarding temperature or current density distribution and, consequently, heat production or type of reaction. For these reasons, the pressure drop of gases and coolant were calculated in this model using the Hardy-Cross method [45]. The model considers locally induced pressure drop, current density distribution, and two-phase flow. In contrast to Huang et al. [45], the cell was segmented in flow direction of the gases and fluids, and the pressure drop of the segments were calculated individually. For a detailed analysis, see Huang et al [45]. In general, the pressure drop in manifolds and cells can be determined as follows:

$$- \text{ In manifolds: } \Delta P^{manifold} = \Delta p_{fric} + \Delta p_{mass} + \Delta p_{geo}$$

- In cells: $\Delta P^{cells} = \Delta p_{geo} + \Delta p_{fric}$

These pressure losses consist of the frictional losses Δp_{fric} , the local pressure losses Δp_{geo} , and the mass losses Δp_{mass} .

Frictional losses occur due to the viscosity of the fluid or gas at the surface of the channel wall:

$$\Delta p_{fric} = \lambda \rho_{mix} \frac{\Delta L u^2}{D}$$

Here, λ is the friction factor, D is the hydraulic diameter, ρ_{mix} is the density, and u is the velocity of the gas mixture or fluid.

Local pressure losses occur because the fluid or gases must change flow direction when entering and exiting the cell due to the geometry of the cells:

$$\Delta p_{geo} = \rho_{mix} K \frac{u^2}{2}$$

where K is the local loss coefficient.

The mass losses are only found in the manifolds, since here the flow rate either decreases as the gases and fluids are distributed from the manifolds into the individual cells or increases as the gases flow again from the cells into the manifolds.

$$\Delta p_{mass} = \Delta \left(\rho_{mix} \frac{u^2}{2} \right)$$

During the fuel cell reaction, water is produced, which can also be present in liquid form. Therefore, the pressure drop of the two-phase flow is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta P_{cells} = \left(1 + \frac{2}{3} C\chi + \frac{1}{2} \chi^2 \right) \Delta P_g$$

The Martinelli parameter χ describes the relationship between the pressure loss of the fluid being only water and the pressure loss of pure gas [45].

1.4.2. Gas crossover

Since the proton pump cell voltage depends on the H₂ content or the gas composition on the cathode, crossover currents of the gases due to partial pressure differences across the membrane cannot be neglected. With Fick's law, the hydrogen [46] crossover flux \dot{n}_{H_2} through the membrane is

$$\dot{n}_{H_2} = \varepsilon_{H_2,diff} \Delta p_{H_2,mem} / d$$

With the hydrogen permeability of the membrane $\varepsilon_{H_2,diff}$, the hydrogen pressure difference on both sides of the membrane $\Delta p_{H_2,mem}$ and the thickness of the membrane d .

The H₂ crossover flux through the membrane is directly proportional to the H₂ pressure. Since the cathodic hydrogen pressure is negligible, the hydrogen partial pressure at the membrane can be calculated using Darcy's law:

$$p_{H_2,mem} = (p_{an,ch}^2 - K_{H_2} i_{seg})^{0.5}$$

With $K_{H_2} = 2 \cdot \frac{(d_{CL} K_{GDL} + d_{an,GDL} K_{CL}) R T_{H_2} \mu_{H_2}}{F K_{CL} K_{GDL} M_{H_2}}$

Here, the pressure losses between the flow channels and the GDL, as well as between the GDL and the CL, were considered. $d_{CL,GDL}$ is the thickness of CL and GDL, $K_{CL,GDL}$ is the permeability of the GDL and CL, R is the universal gas constant, F is the Faraday constant, i_{seg} is the current density, T_{H_2} is the H₂ gas temperature, M is the molar mass, and μ_{H_2} is the fluid viscosity. The H₂ permeability of the membrane can be calculated using the Arrhenius equation:

$$\varepsilon_{H_2,diff} = \varepsilon_{H_2,diff,0} \exp(-E_{H_2,diff} / RT_{mem})$$

With $\varepsilon_{H_2,diff,0}$ being the hydrogen maximum permeability coefficient

$$\varepsilon_{H_2,diff,0} = \varepsilon_{H_2,1} \exp(\varepsilon_{H_2,2} a_{an})$$

and $E_{H_2,diff}$ being the hydrogen activation energy for diffusion

$$E_{H_2,diff} = E_{H_2,1} \exp(E_{H_2,2} a_{an})$$

$\varepsilon_{H_2,1,2}$ and $E_{H_2,1,2}$ were taken from Omrani et al [46].

The nitrogen crossover flux can be calculated the same way. Further information can be found in Omrani et al. [46] and Wu et al. [47].

1.4.3. Water transport

The water transport in and within the membrane can be described with the following source terms [48-50]:

$$S_{mem} = S_{EOD} + S_{TOS} + S_{diff} + S_{sorp} + S_{prod}$$

The source term of water transport consists of the electroosmotic drag S_{EOD} , the thermoosmosis S_{TOS} , the diffusion between cathode and anode S_{diff} , the sorption of pores to ionomer S_{sorp} and the water generation in the cathode semi reaction S_{prod} . The detailed source terms for water transfer can be found in Table 1.

Transport mechanism	Water transport function
Electro osmotic drag [48]	$S_{EOD} = n_d \frac{i_{seg}}{nF}$
Thermo osmosis [49]	$S_{TOS} = \frac{D_{H_2O,T}}{d} (T_{ca} - T_{an})$
Diffusion [50]	$S_{diff} = \frac{D_{H_2O,diff}}{d} (\lambda_{mem,ca} - \lambda_{mem,an})$
Water sorption [38]	$S_{sorp} = k_{sorp} \frac{\rho_{mem}}{EW_{mem}} (\lambda_{mem,equil} - \lambda_{mem})$
Water generation	$S_{prod} = \frac{i_{seg}}{nF}$

$$n_d = \begin{cases} 1 & \lambda_{mem} \leq 14.72 \\ \left(1 + \frac{1.5}{22-14.72}\right) \cdot (\lambda_{mem} - 14.72) & \lambda_{mem} > 14.72 \end{cases}$$

Further information can be found in [38].

1.5. Simulation scheme

The model calculates both the cell voltage and the current density in each element along the flow direction. For this reason, multiple iteration steps are necessary. The outer iteration is used to calculate the cell voltage, during which the cell voltage V_{cell} is iteratively modified until the current calculated in the middle loop corresponds to the requested current I_{set} . The middle iteration calculates the current density in each segment. However, if the requested current I_{set} cannot be provided solely by the fuel cell reaction, a decision is made in the innermost loop as to whether the respective segment will be fuel cell reaction or proton pump reaction. For this purpose, the limit value of the minimum oxygen partial pressure for the fuel cell reaction is adjusted. This iteration is repeated until the requested current I_{set} corresponds to the actual current I_{act} .

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

The experiments were conducted with a fuel cell stack with 335 cells in a fuel cell system including an Air system, a hydrogen system with a Jet Pump and a passive recirculation loop, a thermal system with a coolant pump and a cooler with a bypass and an electrical system. The Vehicle Control Unit (VCU) evaluates the power demand outside of the fuel cell system. The Fuel Cell Control Unit (FCCU) controls the subsystems based on this power demand. On the fuel cell stack, the cell voltage is measured with both single CVM and double CVM (i.e. one voltage tap per two cells) at the cathode inlet and outlet, respectively.

Fig. 2: Air starvation tests: O₂ stoichiometry jumps. a) lambda air (blue) + mass fraction of gasses (H₂ red, O₂ black) at cathode outlet. b) current (red) and cell + stack voltages. Caution: stack voltage is in V. The black lines in a) and b) indicate the point of time $t_1 - t_5$ of the single CVM c) - g).

The temperature of starvation experiments is set at a normal operation temperature of ca. 60°C. The current set point is set to 113 A during the experiment of air starvation. To start the experiment, the stack was operated with overstoichiometric air supply. After the oxygen concentration in the exhaust gas stabilized and a steady-state point was reached, the oxygen stoichiometry was gradually reduced and kept constant for approximately 15–20 seconds per each stoichiometry set point. The H₂ stoichiometry was maintained at an overstoichiometric level throughout the experiment to prevent a possible anode undersupply. A mass spectrometer directly at the cathode outlet measures and analyzes the gas composition.

Fig. 2 shows an overview of different physical quantities under galvanostatic condition at 113 A with different air stoichiometry conditions. Fig 2a) illustrates the air stoichiometry curve from 1.4 to 1.2x. In the same picture the molar fractions of H₂ and O₂ in the cathode outlet gas are depicted. Fig. 2b) exhibits the real-time output of minimal, maximum and mean cell voltage as well as the drawn current and the stack voltage during the experiment. Fig. 2c) - g) picture the single CVM of the whole stack measured at the point of times t₁ – t₅, highlighted in Fig. 2a) and b. For clarity, only the single CVM is shown in Fig. 2. The black line in Fig. 2c) - g) indicates the OCV of the proton pump [34].

3. Results

3.1. Air starvation experiments

As already mentioned, one possible strategy for successfully performing a freeze start is the so-called air starvation. In this method, the (effective) air lambda is restricted to values close to 1, thus limiting the oxygen supply. As can be seen in Fig. 3a), the concentration overvoltage increases sharply due to oxygen limitation, while the cell voltage decreases although the current density stays constant. The operating point thus shifts from the blue point (air overstoic operation point) to the orange point (air understoic operation point).

Fig. 3 a) U-I characteristic curve for air overstoic operation (blue) and air understoic operation (orange). With air understoic operation, the efficiency of cell deteriorates due to increased diffusion losses. Adapted from [9]. b) and c) Different reaction equations in fuel cells at different operational points.

This reduces the efficiency of the fuel cell, causing increased waste heat production at a constant current density (yellow area + yellow-purple-dashed area) and the fuel cell to heat up more quickly. One advantage, however, is that electrical current can still be drawn (purple area) [9]. This behavior is clearly visible in Fig. 2 in the first 40 seconds. With reduced oxygen stoichiometry, the average cell voltage decreases, but the current remains unchanged. In t₁ the oxygen concentration decreases to almost 0% and the corresponding minimal cell voltage decreases accordingly. In Fig. 2c) the single cell voltages are shown.

Individual cell voltages are already beginning to drop. However, the majority of cell voltages remain above 0.6 V. What is striking, however, is that the individual cell voltages are not stable or even constant but are already beginning to fluctuate. As can be seen in Fig.2 a), the hydrogen concentration on the cathode side is still constant during this phase. Therefore, no additional hydrogen appears to be being pumped from anode to cathode.

Since the oxygen supply is limited, it may happen that the required current cannot be achieved with the existing oxygen content at the catalyst layer using the conventional fuel cell reaction due to the current continuity in the series connection of the cells.

However, as can be seen in the experiments shown in Fig. 2, the required current is constantly drawn. This leads to the assumption that an alternative reaction must take place on the cathode side within the cells (see Fig. 3b)).

Since the hydrogen concentration on the anode is sufficient, but the oxygen concentration on the cathode isn't, the so-called hydrogen pump effect occurs. In this effect, the hydrogen oxidized at the anode recombines back into hydrogen after passing through the proton exchange membrane on the cathode [40-42]: $2 H^+$ (anode) + $2 e^- = H_2$ (cathode).

If the air stoichiometry is further reduced, which increases the current ratio contributing to the proton pump, the cell voltage continues to drop and can even reach a negative cell voltage. As can be seen in Fig. 2a), both reactions occur simultaneously, since oxygen is present at the cathode inlet but not at the cathode outlet. At a certain O_2 stoichiometry (here 1.3), the oxygen is completely converted, and only hydrogen, nitrogen, and water vapor remain in the cathode exhaust.

Although the cells were still driven overstoic, they started to show limitation behavior in the cell voltages. There can be different reasons for that. One possibility is, that there might be uncertainties related to the mass flow measurement, since the mass flow at stoichiometries that low is hard to measure. But Xia et al. [51] have found a similar O_2 stoichiometry at which the starvation starts to occur. They found out, the higher the current the higher the contradiction between mass transfer demand inside the cell and the slow kinetics of ORR. This means that limiting behavior can already occur during over-stoichiometric operation.

This can be seen at t_2 : although the air stoichiometry was held constant at 1.3, the minimal cell voltage decreases below the OCV of the proton pump [34].

The single cell voltages in Fig. 2d) show this behavior in multiple cells. However, these cells are still randomly distributed in the stack. What is striking here, as already indicated in Fig. 2c), is the highly dynamic cell voltages distributed across the entire stack. This suggests that even small changes in mass flow at the cell inlet led to strong changes in the cell voltages and that the cells are already in the region of the U-I characteristic curve where the concentration overvoltage increases sharply.

At t_3 , the average cell voltage drops sharply and, correspondingly, the H_2 concentration in the exhaust gas increases. Since the stoichiometry was not maintained long enough in t_3 , a constant hydrogen concentration is not established here. In the CVM signals in Fig. 2e), most of the cell voltages have already dropped to the proton pump OCV level, which explains the sharply increasing hydrogen concentration in the exhaust gas. Particularly striking here is the beginning of a certain clustering of cell voltages that are still above 0.6 V. Potential underlying reasons will be discussed later.

If the O_2 stoichiometry is further reduced (time t_4), more and more cell voltages drop. Individual cells remain above 0.6 V. This randomness can be attributed to the highly dynamic nature of the transport limitation, as well as to the dynamic mass flow changes at the inlet due to pressure losses. Even small changes in humidity or gas composition can lead to a significant change in pressure loss. Here, too, the various cell voltage blocks are still visible, but far less prominent than at time t_3 . The O_2 stoichiometry was maintained long enough for the hydrogen concentration to reach equilibrium. However, the cell voltage continues to drop. Between time t_4 and time t_5 , the O_2 stoichiometry was increased to the same level as at time t_3 . The hydrogen concentration decreases, while the average cell voltage increases slightly again. Interestingly, the cell voltages remain lower than before with the same stoichiometry. This is probably due to the fact that the oxygen reservoirs in the canals continue to be starved.

3.2. Simulation of Air starvation

Fig. 4: Simulation results of air starvation. a) The simulated and experimentally determined cell and stack voltages. b) Segmentation along the flow direction shows that the fuel cell and proton pump reactions occur simultaneously.

Fig. 4a) shows the simulation results of the described model with the same input variables as the air starvation experiments. As can be seen, the simulated cell voltage qualitatively describes the course of the experimentally determined cell voltage.

The measurement data in Fig. 2c) - g) show that the individual cells perform differently. This can occur either due to different pressure drops in the cells or manifolds or due to different precious metal loading. Uneven distribution of gases can lead to malfunctions in the chemical reactions within the stack and the cells. This can lead to, for example, either an undersupply of the cells or flooding if the gases flow too slowly and can no longer remove the water. This can result in a reduced service life. If, on the other hand, too much gas flows through the cells, humidity decreases, and the membrane dries out.

If this behavior occurs during an O_2 stoichiometric undersupply, some cells are undersupplied, and others oversupplied as depicted in Fig. 2e) - g) by the strongly varying cell voltages distributed across the stack: as already mentioned, cell voltages of those cells that are undersupplied with O_2 drop to approximately 50 mV, which is below the OCV of the proton pump for this setup and operating point [34].

Therefore, the simulated cell voltage is compared with the minimal cell voltage of the experiment since the model does not take uneven gas distribution due to design deviations or uneven, precious metal loading into account.

The slopes of the minimum cell voltage and the simulated cell voltage do not match in the first 20 s. This is because the cell which represents the minimum voltage in this time range is damaged and measures a maximum of approximately 275 mV. As soon as this value is undercut, simulation and experiment agree qualitatively well. If one compares the curve of the stack voltage and the simulated voltage, the curves qualitatively agree with each other, with a slight time offset.

This is a relic for the reasons mentioned above: the stack voltage and the average voltage describe the average and therefore all cells, regardless of whether they have different cell voltages due to loading or design. Therefore, the stack voltage only drops noticeably when not just one cell voltage drops, but several. Therefore, the reduction in cell voltage occurs with a time lag. However, since the simulation describes this process very well, it shows that the model represents air starvation very well despite the lack of integration of malfunctions due to the design and loading of the MEA.

The voltage curve of the simulation shows a kink at $t = 23$ s, in contrast to the experimental cell and stack voltage. This kink is due to the modeling of discrete switching between the fuel cell reaction and the proton pump reaction.

Fig. 5b) depicts the individual overpotential losses of the respective segments. The longitudinal dimension of the cell is described by x . 0 represents the cathode inlet and 1 the cathode outlet. This figure confirms the hypothesis that the fuel cell reaction and proton pump reaction occur simultaneously in the cell during oxygen starvation (Fig. 3c). In the segments with the lowest oxygen content at the cathode outlet (here: last segment), the alternative reaction (proton pump) occurs as soon as the required current can no longer be produced solely by the fuel cell reaction. The main reaction zone during air starvation operation mode decreases with decreasing oxygen stoichiometry and moves towards the cathode inlet. As soon as there is enough oxygen concentration in the cell again to fulfill the required current, the type of reaction switches back to normal fuel cell operation mode (Fig. 3b)).

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